

THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND PRECIPITATION ON WHEAT AND BARLEY CROPS IN SOME PROVENANCE OF IRAQ

Rana Khaled Hussein Trad

*Al-Karkh University of Science College of Energy and Environmental Sciences
Department of Environmental Sciences*

Sara Shaheed Obayes Jaber

Al Qasim Green University College of Environmental Sciences Department Environmental Pollution

Aymen Sultan Ibrahim Hussein

*University of Mosul College of Environmental Science and Technology Department:
Environmental Science*

Hussein Ibrahim Hilal Saleh

*University of Mosul College of Environmental Sciences and Technologies
Department of Environmental Technologies*

Othman Ahmed Ayoub Suleman

University of mosul College of environmental Science and Technology Departmen: Environmental science

Abstract: This work investigates the effect of two important climate parameters (temperature and precipitation) on the cultivation and production of wheat and barley crops in the period 2015–2021. It was analyzed the relationship between crop productivity and two climatic variables for three Iraqi stations, Baghdad, Diyala, and Maysan, with the aim of revealing the potential climatic conditions for their cultivation and production in those stations.

Where climate change affects agriculture in several ways, including: changes in temperature rates, precipitation, and extreme weather fluctuations (such as: heat waves); changes in pests and diseases. This study was based on production data and climate data, Climate data Daily data on minimum and maximum temperatures and precipitation in three stations had been collected from the Iraqi meteorological organization and seismology (the Climate Center) in Baghdad, for the period 2015–2021. As for Crop production data was collected from the ministry of planning, central bureau of statistics, wheat and barley reports (published data).

The results showed that the relationship between wheat productivity and the annual average temperature was positively correlated in Baghdad, where it was negative in Maysan and Diyala, while the correlation between wheat productivity and precipitation was positive before 2020 in Baghdad, and was negatively correlated in Maysan and Diyala. Whereas for the barley crop, it was negatively correlated with the average annual temperature over the entire study area (Baghdad, Maysan, and Diyala). And was also negatively related to precipitation in all three stations.

1.1 Introduction

Despite advances in technology and widespread irrigation, agricultural production is still highly dependent on the weather. A quantitative understanding of crop responses to climate requires the development of numerical models with the response of interest (e.g., crop yield, quality, value of farmland) as the dependent variable and various climate-related quantities (e.g., incremental precipitation and average temperature) as the predictor(s) (Wilkinson et al.2002). Environmental variables play an important role in determining the productivity and quality of agricultural crops. Agricultural production in any region controls its production by some environmental variables, and any crop has a certain level of environmental needs that must be met for its production. Accordingly, agricultural crops vary in their environmental needs. Various scholars have reported changes in climate parameters in different world regions. Regional temperatures increased significantly in the 20th century (Banda et al.2012; Jiao et al.2012). The temperature rise has been even more noticeable so far in the 21st century (ipcc2014). The changes are visible in global and regional precipitation patterns as the Earth's rain belts are redistributing (Putnam & Broecker 2017). Consequently, the temperature and precipitation variability/trends are affecting crop yields (Lobell & Field 2007; Asseng et al.2015). It has been suggested that the global wheat yields would reduce by 6% with an increase of each degree Celsius in global mean temperature (zhao et al. 2017). Climate variability directly influences agricultural production and yields (mall et al. 2006; Birthal et al.2014). The rise in temperature and changes in precipitation have adversely affected crop production (Alejo 2021). Governments and farmers can manage non-climatic factors but find it difficult to alter the impact of climate, particularly temperature and precipitation, on crop yields (Alemayehu & Bewket 2016). Agricultural cultivation depends mainly on the climate; Therefore, the impact of climate change and variability on agricultural production and yields is significant (Eticha et al. 2021). In general, the occurrence of extreme weather events, such as temperature extremes or extreme precipitation patterns, may cause severe crop damage, but when temperature extremes and precipitation conditions intertwine, the damage caused by extreme weather may be moderate (Aleshina et al. 2021). For example, during high temperatures, plants can emit water through higher evapotranspiration to prevent heat damage (Hernandez et al.2016). To date, few studies have investigated the combined effect of extreme temperature and extreme precipitation patterns on crop yields on a global scale (Lee & Bae et al. 2011).

In more than 50% of the studies, it was found that the effect of high temperature is the most negative on crop productivity. Crop productivity is improving in some regions, while it is declining in other regions of the world (Karimi et al., 2018; Kristensen et al.,2011). This difference is due to many factors, such as precipitation, increased carbon dioxide and increased temperature. An increase in temperature leads to an increase in crop transpiration and evaporation of soil water. It also leads to an increase in soil aridity and thus negatively affects the growth and productivity of crops (Daba et al., 2016; Leisner, 2020). There are very few studies on climate change adaptation in Iraq due to conditions of political instability since the 1980s, which has led to reduced funding and support for agricultural and environmental research (Daham et al., 2003, 2019; Jaradat). Therefore, the effect of high temperature on crop growth and productivity in Iraq has not been studied. This study came to assess the impact of climate change on strategic crops and irrigation efficiency.

The effects of climatic elements on crop growth and productivity have been studied in a wide range of research.

2.2 Aim of the study

this study focuses on the impact of two important elements of the climate on agriculture and the production of wheat and barley crops, with the aim of revealing the climatic potential for its cultivation and production at the level of three regions in Iraq.

2.1 Literature review

2.1.1 Previous local studies

- In this study, the climatic potential for the cultivation of wheat and barley crops was revealed in two of the governorates of Iraq (Sondus Muhammad Alwan and Kawthar Nasser Abbas, 2020).
- In this study, (RZWQMZ) the root zone model was used to simulate the effects of climate change on actual water consumption, water use efficiency of wheat and barley, their productivity, and ways to adapt to climate change (saadi Sattar, Sohair and other,2022).

2.1.2 Previous international studies

- In this study, the relationship between crop yield and three climate variables (minimum temperature, maximum temperature, and precipitation) was analyzed (Kimberly A. Nicholas, Christopher and other,2007).
- In this study, which was conducted in Poland, the temperature and precipitation conditions were evaluated on the dynamics of plant growth and development and its effect on precipitation. (Elżbieta JĘDRSZCZYK^{1*}, Barbaraa and other,2016).
- In this study, complex relationships were found between extreme heat and precipitation patterns as well as compounding effects on the major crop (wheat) in South Asia (Xinyi Fan, Duoping and other, 2022).

2.2 Overview of the climate of Iraq

Iraq is located within the northern temperate zone, but the climate is continental and subtropical. Winters are typically mild to cold, with the average daily temperature reaching 16°C and nighttime lows of 0°C. Summers are dry and hot to sweltering, with the shade temperature exceeding 45°C during the summer months, however it drops at night to 26°C. Precipitation follows a Mediterranean climate, with most precipitation falling during winter, spring and autumn. There is no precipitation during the summer. The average annual precipitation is 154 mm, and ranges from less than 100 mm in` of the country in the south to 1200 mm in the north-east (Ewaid et al.,2019).

Most parts of Iraq, according to the amounts of precipitation and prevailing temperatures, are located within what is known as the dry and semi-arid climatic regions of the world. Therefore, the most important effects of climate change on the country's ecosystem are mainly reflected in the agricultural system and its water supply (Hassan 2021, and Kadhum, 2021; Hassan and Nile). rainfall and an increase in the frequency of droughts compared to before

The form of wheat and barley crops are the main part of rain-fed agriculture in Iraq, as the percentage Percentage of the areas cultivated with both crops within the rain. The fragility of rain-fed agriculture in light of climatic changes is the result of the great fluctuation in the amount of rainfall from year to year. In addition to the variation in the amounts of its fall from one month to another during the months of the winter season or its recession sometimes, whether at the beginning or at the end of the agricultural season. As this is reflected in a negative impact on the productivity of crops grown in those lands, and perhaps what increases the fragility of rain-fed agriculture is that the rains begin to recede at the end of the spring season at a time when the cultivated grain crops, especially wheat, are in an advanced stage of maturity and need additional rain, which causes water stress. on the plant is negatively reflected in the yield of the crop, Sometimes the crop is almost completely lost and not harvested (Shahada et al.,2022).

2.3 wheat crop

The wheat crop is one of the basic food crops in human life, and it was mentioned in the heavenly books that emphasized the importance of this crop. It is the most cultivated and widespread field crop in most parts

of the world. 35% of the world's population depends on it for their livelihood. Wheat protein contains A percentage ranging between 30-35% of gluten, which helps in making the best types of bread Compared to the rest of the other types of grain crops, certain types of wheat are used in many food industries that people need, as well as being included in Pharmaceutical industries (dextrose and sucrose), and its residues are used as animal feed. Wheat production in Iraq was concentrated in the Demi region (northern Iraq), which is subject to. Due to the conditions of risk and uncertainty due to its production being linked to fluctuating climatic conditions and the adoption of traditional patterns in production, which resulted in the inability of supply to meet the need for local demand for it due to the dependence of local production on continuous irrigation (Ghazal et al., 2010). The wheat crop is a crop that is suitable for a climate that is moderately hot, inclined to cold, and has moderate humidity (saad et al., 2013). It needs a temperature of not less than 15C°. Its production is good at high temperatures and an increase in the radiation period at the end of the growing season. The growth period extends to more than three months. The winter wheat crop is sown in late autumn and continues to grow in the winter and matures in late spring or early summer (EL-shabini, ganal Mohamed, 2009). and the length of the growing season for winter wheat extends from (65) months to ripen. It is harvested in late summer. Wheat may be exposed to moisture stress as a result of its extreme sensitivity to water deficiency in some growth stages, such as germination, branching and flowering, which reduces the amount of grain yield (Abdel-Hamid Ahmed El-Younes et al., 1978). As for the accumulated heat or the amount of thermal energy that the plant needs during its growth season, wheat needs from (1700-1900) thermal units, and barley needs (1500) thermal units (Ali Ali Al-Khashen et al., 1963). The temperature is one of the important factors affecting the growth and quantity of the wheat crop, and the appropriate temperatures for wheat vary according to the stages of growth. Wheat needs a temperature of not less than 25C°. Its production is good due to the high temperature and the increase in the solar radiation period at the end of the growing season, and the growth period extends to more than (3) months. Wheat grains germinate at a temperature between 5-33C°. The optimum temperature is 25-31C°. The growth of wheat seedlings corresponds to relatively higher temperatures than those required for grain germination. In general, unsuitable temperatures at any stage of wheat growth lead to harmful effects on growth and a decrease in the quantity of the crop (Al - Hafi, Abdullah Qassem et al., 1981). As for the amount of rain needed by the wheat crop, it depends on the prevailing temperature in the crop cultivation area, and it ranges between (400-1200) mm of annual rain. It has been proven that the lack of rain amounts is considered the important and determining environmental factor in the production of the wheat crop, but in the event that rain water is not available in sufficient quantities, wheat is not grown unless there is irrigation water, which is what is known as irrigated agriculture (The Ministry of Planning, 2015-2021).

3.1 Materials and Methods

3.1.1 Study Area

The study area includes three Iraqi governorates: represented by the governorates of Baghdad, Diyala and Maysan for the period from 2015 to 2021 as shown in Figure (3.1).

Figure (3.1): Study area location from Iraq

3.2 Data sources

3.2.1 Climate data

Daily data on minimum and maximum temperatures and precipitation in three stations had been collected from the Iraqi meteorological organization and seismology (the Climate Center) in Baghdad,

3.2.2 Crop data

The annual wheat and barley production data in three stations during the period (2015 -2021) was collected from the ministry of planning, central bureau of statistics, wheat and barley reports (published data).

(Results and Discussion)

4.1 The relationship between the wheat productivity, temperature and Precipitation.

4.1.1 The relationship between the wheat production and temperature.

Figure (4.2) shows the relationship between wheat productivity and annual mean temperature in Baghdad, there is a positive relationship between wheat productivity and annual temperature as we can see from the figure, wheat the highest temperature occurs in the year of 2017 and the mine mum temperature recorded al the year of 2019. whereas the productivity of the wheat crop was lowest value at the year of 2016 and the highest value at the year of 2021.

Figure (4.3) shows the relationship between wheat productivity and Annual mean temperature in maysan .it is clear that the negative Relationship between wheat productivity and annual mean temperature as we can see from the figure, highest temperature occurs in the year of 2021 and the minimum temperature recorded at the year of 2016. whereas the productivity of the wheat crop was lowest value at the year of 2019 and the highest value at the year of 2017.

Figure (4.4) shows the relationship between wheat productivity and Annual mean temperature in Diyala. there is a negative relationship between wheat productivity and annual mean temperature as we can see from the figure. the highest temperature occurred in the of 2021 and lowest temperature recorded at the year 2015. while productivity of the wheat crop was highest value at the year of 2020, the lowest value was at the year of 2015.

figure (4.2) The relationship between the wheat production and temperature(C°) wheat in Baghdad.

figure (4.3) The relationship between the wheat production and temperature(C°) wheat in maysan.

figure (4.4) The relationship between the wheat production and temperature(C°) wheat in Diyala.

4.1.2 The relationship between the wheat production and precipitation.

Figure (4.5) shows the relationship between wheat productivity and precipitation in Baghdad. It is clear that there is a positive relationship between wheat yield and precipitation. as you can see from the figure, where the highest precipitation occurs in the year of 2018 and the minimum precipitation recorded at the year 2021. whereas the productivity of the wheat crop was lowest value at the year of 2016 and the highest value at the year of 2021.

Figure (4.6) shows the relationship between wheat productivity and precipitation in Maysan. It is clear that there is a negative relationship between wheat yield and precipitation as you can see from the figure, where the highest precipitation occurs in the year of 2018 and the minimum precipitation recorded at the year 2017. Whereas the productivity of the wheat crop was lowest value at the year of 2019 and the highest value at the year of 2017.

Figure (4.7) shows the relationship between wheat productivity and precipitation, in Diyala. There is a negative relationship between wheat productivity and precipitation. As you can see from the figure, where the highest precipitation occurs in the year of 2018 and the minimum precipitation recorded at the year 2021. Whereas the productivity of the wheat crop was lowest value at the year of 2015 and the highest value at the year of 2020.

figure (4.5) The relationship between the wheat production and precipitation(mm) in Baghdad

figure (4.6) The relationship between the wheat production and precipitation(mm) in Maysan.

figure (4.7) The relationship between the wheat production and precipitation(mm) in diyala.

4.2 The relationship between the Barley productivity, temperature and precipitation.

4.2.1 The relationship between the Barley production temperature.

Figure (4.8) shows the relationship between barley productivity and annual mean temperature in Baghdad, there is a negative relationship between barley productivity and annual temperature .as we can see from the figure, barley the highest temperature occurs in the year of 2021 and the minimum temperature recorded at the year of 2016. whereas the productivity of the barley crop was lowest value at the year of 2021 and the highest value at the year of 2015.

figure (4.9) shows the relationship between barley productivity and Annual mean temperature in maysan . there is a negative relationship between barley productivity and annual mean temperature as we can see from the figure. the lowest temperature occurred in the of 2016 ,2019 and highest temperature recorded at the year 2021. while productivity of the barley crop was highest value at the year of 2016, the lowest value was at the year of 2019.

figure (4.10) shows the relationship between barley productivity and Annual mean temperature in diyala. it is clear that a negative relationship between barley productivity and annual mean temperature as we can see from the figure. the highest temperature occurred in the of 2021 and lowest temperature recorded at the year 2016. while productivity of the barley crop was highest value at the year of 2016, the lowest value was at the year of 2018.

figure (4.8) The relationship between the wheat production and temperature(C°) Barley in Baghdad.

figure (4.9) The relationship between the wheat production and temperature(C°) Barley in maysan.

figure (4.10) The relationship between the wheat production and temperature(C°) Barley in Diyala.

4.2.2 The relationship between the Barley production and precipitation.

figure (4.11) shows the relationship between barley productivity and precipitation in Baghdad. it is clear that the negative relationship between barley productivity and precipitation as we can see from the figure. the highest precipitation occurred in the of 2018 and lowest precipitation recorded at the year 2021. while productivity of the barley crop was highest value at the year of 2016, the lowest value was at the year of 2019.

figure (4.12) shows the relationship between barley productivity and precipitation in maysan. it is clear that the negative relationship between barley productivity and precipitation. a as we can see from the figure. the highest precipitation occurred in the of 2018 and lowest precipitation recorded at the year 2017. whereas the productivity of the barley crop was highest value at the year of 2016, the lowest value was at the year of 2015, 2019.

figure (4.13) shows the relationship between barley productivity and precipitation in Diyala . it is clear that the negative relationship between barley productivity and precipitation. as we can see from the figure. the highest precipitation occurred in the of 2018 and lowest precipitation recorded at the year 2021. while as the productivity of the barley crop was highest value at the year of 2016, the lowest value was at the year of 2018.

figure (4.11) The relationship between the barley production and precipitation(mm) Baghdad.

figure (4.12) The relationship between the barley production and precipitation(mm) in maysan.

figure (4.13) The relationship between the barley production and precipitation(mm) Diyala.

5.1 Conclusions

The effect of temperature and precipitation on strategical crops has been one of the major interesting questions in recent works. The present work aims to study the effect of temperature and precipitation on crops over Iraq. And the following points are representing the main conclusion of this Work:

1. The relationship between wheat productivity and annual mean temperature was positively related in Baghdad where was negative in Maysan and Diyala.
2. Wheat productivity related in positive manner with precipitation before 2020 in Baghdad, whereas in Maysan and Diyala was negatively related.
3. Barley related in negative manner with the annual mean temperature over the whole area of study (Baghdad, Maysan, Diyala).
4. The result showed that Barley Also negatively related with precipitation in all three governates.

5.2 Recommendations

According to the above conclusions we recommended some important suggestion that can support future studies:

1. As the effects of climate parameters dose not local impact, it is important to study the effect of climate parameters on strategical crops in a wide range that involve the countries bounded to Iraq.
2. Use another governates, important to improve the results that we have in this work.

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